

Notes on Linear Programming

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Abstract

Quick notes about solving linear programming problems (LLP) graphically. Specifically addresses the question: why does the solution of a LLP often lie at a corner of the feasible area, which bugged me quite a while.

A linear programming problem (LPP) takes the following form

$$\arg \max_{\mathbf{x}} \quad \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{x} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}, \tag{2}$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ are the unknowns, $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$, $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^M$ are the M inequality constraints, and $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ problem specific coefficients.

Instead of the general problem, we study simplified version in \mathbb{R}^2 , i.e. $N = 2$ with $M = 4$ constraints in order to visualize the idea:

$$x^*, y^* = \arg \max_{x,y} \quad g(x,y) = c_1x + c_2y \tag{3}$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad a_{11}x + a_{12}y \leq b_1 \tag{4}$$

$$a_{21}x + a_{22}y \leq b_2 \tag{5}$$

$$-x \leq 0 \tag{6}$$

$$-y \leq 0, \tag{7}$$

where the last 2 constraints are introduced to limit our problem to the first quadrant of a Cartesian coordinate system.

Each of the above linear inequalities define a half-plane in the (x,y) space, bounded by the line obtained by replacing the inequality by equality. For the first constraint, we have

$$y = -\frac{a_{11}}{a_{12}}x + \frac{b_1}{a_{12}}, \tag{8}$$

and similarly for the other constraints. The solution

$$z^* = g(x^*, y^*) \tag{9}$$

Figure 1: Graphical representation of a two-dimensional linear programming problem having two constraints (green and red line). Gray area is the feasible area of solutions. Intersections of constraints are marked with black dots.

that maximizes Equation 3 must therefore lie in the area bounded by the intersection of all half-planes. This area is called the feasible region and is clearly convex. The feasible area for the above problem is illustrated in Figure 1.

Assume a constant utility value $z = g(x, y)$, and plug into Equation 3 to get

$$z = g(x, y) = c_1x + c_2y \tag{10}$$

$$y = -\frac{c_1}{c_2}x + \frac{z}{c_2}. \tag{11}$$

That is, the graph for constant utility is a straight line in the (x, y) space.

Clearly, if we increase the utility z , all we do is increase the intercept of this line. Hence, all possible utilities correspond to parallel lines and z^* corresponds to the largest utility whose graph touches the feasible area. This is illustrated in Figure 2. Notice, the optimal solution always lies at a corner of the polygon (tope), except when the graph of constant utility is parallel to one of the edges of the feasible area (in which case we get a possibly infinite number of solutions (x, y) for z^*).

Final note, depending on the orientation of the graph of the utility function (as defined by the negative ratio between c_1 and c_2) different corners may be selected as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the solution to a linear programming problem. Constraints (green and red line). Gray area is the feasible area of solutions. Intersections of constraints are marked with black dots. Dashed lines represent utility functions for constant utility z . All utility functions are parallel lines and the maximum utility z^* is found by the line with the largest intercept that touches the feasible area.

1 Example

Consider a problem from the funding accounting area: given the staff costs of each partner, maximize the grant amount that can be paid out subject to the following constraints: a) management staff costs per partner must be more than r percent of total staff costs, b) staff costs per partner must be between s and t percent of total staff costs, and c) the grant amount paid out must not exceed the amounts submitted ¹.

1.1 Variables

Formally, we will introduce the following positive variables: Management staff costs per partner

$$\mathbf{x} = (x_1 \quad x_2 \quad \cdots \quad x_N),$$

and other staff costs per partner

$$\mathbf{y} = (y_1 \quad y_2 \quad \cdots \quad y_N).$$

Total staff costs are given by

$$t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_i x_i + \sum_i y_i.$$

¹A Python impl. of this example can be found at <https://gist.github.com/cheind/27062b87009e1dc305590ba729b87f3a>

Figure 3: Graphical representation of the solution to a linear programming problem for a differently oriented utility function. Constraints (green and red line). Gray area is the feasible area of solutions. Intersections of constraints are marked with black dots. Dashed lines represent utility functions for constant utility z . All utility functions are parallel lines and the maximum utility z^* is found by the line with the largest intercept that touches the feasible area.

1.2 Objective

The objective is given by

$$\arg \max_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}} \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{y},$$

with $c = \mathbf{1}$. For convenience we will stack the \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} into

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x} \\ \mathbf{y} \end{pmatrix},$$

so that the objective simplifies to

$$\arg \max_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}} \mathbf{1}^T \hat{\mathbf{x}}.$$

1.3 Constraints

Constraint a) for partner i is formally given by

$$\frac{x_i}{t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} \leq r.$$

In its current form it appears non-linear, but can be transformed as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{x_i}{t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} &\leq r \\
x_i &\leq rt(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\
x_i - rt(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) &\leq 0 \\
x_i - \sum_j rx_j - \sum_j ry_j &\leq 0 \\
(1-r)x_i - \sum_{j \neq i} rx_j - \sum_j ry_j &\leq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that x_i appeared twice in the above derivation: once freely on the left side and once inside $t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ and was accounted for in the last equation.

For constraint b) we write

$$s \leq \frac{x_i + y_i}{t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})} \leq t.$$

Following a similar derivation as for constraint a), the constraint for upper bound t of partner i is given by

$$(1-t)x_i + (1-t)y_i - \sum_{j \neq i} tx_j - \sum_{j \neq i} ty_j \leq 0.$$

The lower bound is transformed to an upper bound by multiplying with -1 , yielding

$$(s-1)x_i + (s-1)y_i + \sum_{j \neq i} sx_j + \sum_{j \neq i} sy_j \leq 0.$$